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MOTIVATIONAL FACTORS AMONG NURSING STAFF IN TERTIARY CARE HOSPITALS-A SURVEY

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ABSTRACT

Objective: To identify the factors influencing Nurse's Work Motivation

Study Design: Cross Sectional Study.

Place and Duration of study: The study was carried out at Department of nursing at PNS Shifa Hospital and Jinnah Postgraduate Medical Centre Karachi, January 2021 to July 2021.

Material and Methods: After the approval of institutional review board and informed consent from study participants, a total of 230 nursing staff, with at least two year of working experience were interviewed by using simple random sampling technique, while nurses on ad hoc or contract basis and those who didn't give written consent were excluded from study. The data was collected with the help of available literature from tertiary care hospitals of Karachi through structured pretested and self-administered questionnaire. SPSS version 20.0 was utilized to analyze and interpret the collected data. To calculate demographic variables of the study participants descriptive analysis was performed. For the categorical variables frequencies and percentages were used. Mean and standard deviation was used for continuous variables.

Results: The mean age was 35.07 ± 7.46 years. The most highlighted motivation type was promotion 207(90%) and salary structures 207(90%) and least was strict or constant hospital supervision 94 (41%). The MRS (Aggregated score based on responses) was 1840 with mean 613.3 (SD = 521.0).

Conclusion: Motivational factors include both financial and non-financial and in current study financial incentives, better salary structure, proper performance appraisal system and acknowledgement of nursing job were identified as the important factors of motivation.

Keywords: Factors, Motivation, Nurses, Tertiary Care Hospital

INTRODUCTION

Nursing is a noble profession that is evolving and modernizing with the passage of time; it began in the Islamic era with the care of injured people during and after war¹. It comes up with numerous specialties, including highly qualified PhD Nurses, depending on the situation, from delivering a baby to dressing an injured person. Nursing developed professionally sound practically assembled, and research oriented along with the modernization of the globe². The Honorable President of the Republic of Pakistan declared 2019 to

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be Nurses Year in Pakistan, with WHO declaring 2020 to be the International Year of Nursing and Midwifery. As a result, nursing is a rapidly growing field in Pakistan, with a high level of youth enthusiasm in this field³.

Pakistan is the world's sixth most populated country, with a population of around 180 million people and a literacy rate of 59.9%. Sindh is Pakistan's second most populous province, with a population of more than 50 million people and a literacy rate over 60%⁴. In Pakistan, the nursing profession is rapidly evolving, with nurses experimenting with new and innovative nursing care practices. Nursing shortages have been a major concern for health-care systems all across the world in recent years, including in Pakistan⁵. This scarcity has been linked to nurse dissatisfaction, and it has posed a threat to patient care quality⁶.

This fact becomes considerably more alarming as the population rises, increasing illness prevalence and, as a result, the number of cases. As a result, taking into account the nurses' psychological requirements, job satisfaction and motivation is a critical factor in retaining nurses in the organization⁷. Nurses' work motivation and the elements that influence it are urgently needed on a national and worldwide level, as they have a direct impact on the nursing workforce's preservation, performance, and, as a result, patient outcomes. Such data must be gathered in order to develop appropriate work motivating approaches that will improve nurse performance and reduce turnover. Exploration of this issue will have repercussions for the development and improvement of nursing administration and management as a whole⁸.

It has been noticed that the public health system in low- and middle-income nations lacks high-quality patient care⁸. Low pay, promotions, compensation, fringe benefits, and an inefficient service structure are all demotivating factors for nurses, which have resulted in a slew of demonstrations in recent years, adding to patients' misery⁹.

Despite the fact that nurses' motivation was an important part of health system performance, it was relatively understudied¹⁰. In both the private and public sectors, the local health-care system lacks sufficient data on nurse motivation. Therefore, the main purpose of this study was to identify factors associated with work motivation among nurses.

Material and Methods:

This descriptive cross-sectional study was carried from January 2021 to July 2021, amongst the nurses of PNS Shifa hospital and Jinnah postgraduate Medical Centre Karachi. Data was collected through probability simple random sampling techniques. Total 230 nurses were interviewed in this study using simple random sampling technique. Nurses having at least two years' work experience in these hospitals were included in the study while nurses on contract or ad hoc basis and who refused for written consent were excluded from study. The data was collected after written formal consent. This project was approved prior to data collection by the University-affiliated Institutional Review Board and Ethics Committee. The data was collected by the researcher through structured pretested and self-administered questionnaire developed with the help of available literature from tertiary care hospitals of Karachi and subjects were asked to fill a self-report questionnaire on an individual basis. Participants were reassured for data confidentiality by using anonymity procedure. The questionnaire gathered socio demographic data from the respondents including motivational factors. Data was analyzed by using SPSS version 20.0. Descriptive analysis was performed to calculate demographic variables of the study participants. Frequencies with percentages were calculated for the categorical variables. Mean and standard deviation was calculated for continuous variables.

Results:

The mean age of the participants was 35.07 ± 7.46 . The length of the participants' work experience ranged from 1 to 30 years (11.48 ± 7.25). Other characteristics of the participants are shown in Table-I.

The most highlighted motivation type was promotion 207 (90%) and salary structures 207 (90%) followed by achievements 184 (80%), conditions which include shift changes and prolong working hours, affect the patients care 152 (66%), recognition 138 (60%), more responsibilities 15 (50%), adherence to the hospital policies encourage you to work better 94 (41%) and strict or constant hospital supervision 94 (41%). The MRS (Aggregated score based on responses) was 1840 with mean 613.3 ± 521 (Table-II).

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Table-I: Demographic Details of the Patients (n=230)

Descriptive Statistics	n (%)
Age (Years) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 20-35 36-45 46+ Mean \pm SD	83 (36%) 120 (52%) 27 (12%) 35.07 \pm 7.46
Gender <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Female Male 	198 (86.2%) 32(13.8%)
Marital Status <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Married Unmarried 	122 (53%) 108 (47%)
Residential Status <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Urban Rural 	156(67.8%) 74(32.2%)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Bachelors Masters Diploma 	208 (90.6%) 9(3.9%) 13(5.5%)
Work Experience (years) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1-2 3-4 5+ Mean \pm SD	18(8%) 67(29%) 145(63%) 11.48 \pm 7.25

Table-II: Motivational Factors among Nurses

Educational Status Motivational Factors Questions (Q)	Agree n (%)	Disagree n (%)	Not Sure n (%)	n
Q-1: Success or achievement that you get from the hospital motivates you	184 (80%)	35 (15%)	11(4.7%)	230
Q-2: Recognition as important in the hospital motivates you	138 (60%)	76 (33%)	16 (7%)	230
Q-3: Promotion motivates you to work better	207 (90%)	14 (6%)	9 (4%)	230
Q-4: More responsibilities motivates you	115 (50%)	92 (40%)	23 (10%)	230
Q-5: Does increase in salary or bonus encourage you to work better	207 (90%)	9 (4%)	14 (6%)	230
Q-6: Does strict or constant hospital supervision affect the way you care for	110 (48%)	67 (29%)	53 (23%)	230
Q-7: Do strict hospital policies encourage you to work better	94 (41%)	53 (23%)	83 (36%)	230
Q-8: Do working conditions including long working hours and shift exchange affect the care you render to patients	152 (66%)	55 (24%)	23 (10%)	230
Q-9: MRS (Aggregated score based on responses)	1207	401	232	1840

Discussion:

Human resource management is one of the variables that affects an organization's performance^{11,12}. Human resource management, including acquiring and keeping the correct workers, is the main issue in developing

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countries, particularly in the health sector¹³. Nowadays, motivation is critical in tackling difficulties related to the health workforce¹¹. Exploring the factors that influence motivation may thus provide useful information for improving the quality of healthcare workers' job and performance.

The findings of this study revealed some key motivational elements among nurses working in Karachi's private hospitals. Payment, promotion, benefit, and recognition are four kinds of elements that have a strong association with motivation, according to the literature^{11,14}. In our study, 80% of nurses were motivated when they were successful and had new knowledge, skills, and the ability to grow while working in the hospital, as supported by Muller-Smith¹⁵, who concluded that nurses who recognized the potential for growth rather than the fear of losing invested energy and excitement will lead to a joyful workplace and a strong sense of accomplishment.

The first of the motivated intrinsic elements, recognition or complete appreciation of work done, is ranked highest (87%), demonstrating that most nurses want to be recognized for a job well done.

This is supported by a similar analysis by Wiley¹⁶, who placed this factor first in 1946 and second regularly between 1980 and 1922. Campbell et al¹⁷ discovered in another study that nurses required more acknowledgment to satisfy their requirements for notoriety, prestige, and respect from others, all of which led to increased self-esteem. In a study conducted by Dar S¹⁸ in a tertiary care hospital in Karachi, Pakistan, acknowledgement for achievement was identified as a strong motivational component.

Promotion (90 percent) came in second among the motivational elements in this study. This finding is supported by comparable research by Ebong¹⁹, although it contradicts the findings of previous studies by Kovach²⁰, Wiley¹⁶, and Lindner²¹, who rated the same factor 6th, 4th, and 5th, respectively. The fact that advancement is ranked second strongly supports the Herzberg hypothesis of nursing motivation. In addition, Yin and Yang²² conducted research and concluded that power and position would increase the likelihood of workers remaining in institutions. This is because people are driven by their jobs when they engage in decision-making and have a say in how things are done.

According to the findings, nurses feel motivated when they have a lot of obligations (50%); this is in line with a study done by May²³, who adds that nurses feel inspired when they know they have a lot of duty and autonomy. Lack of autonomy among nurses, insufficient staffing, and work overload, according to Khowaja et al²⁴, could impair job satisfaction, which in turn affects nursing care and production. Ninety percent of the nurses in this study believed that a raise in salary and bonus was a motivating element.

According to a study conducted by Yin and Yang²², nurses who are well compensated in terms of income and fringe benefits are satisfied and work tirelessly. Pay, on the other hand, was regarded as a hygiene aspect in any employment, according to Herzber²⁵, who suggested that an increase in salary or wages motivated employees, but that they were expected to seek the next wage increase. However, Liou et al²⁶ asserted that wage increases are the most important factor in increasing job satisfaction among nurses. Similarly, Dar S, et al¹⁸ mentioned that financial incentives played important roles in nurses' motivation and it was also stated by majority of the nurses included in their research.

According to the findings, 48% of nurses believe that strict (constant) hospital supervision will have an impact on the services they provide to their patients. This contradicts the findings of Nilsson and Stomberg²⁷, who found that opportunities for growth, working conditions, and supervision all aid in improving work performance. We also discovered that the majority of nurses (66%) believe that poor working circumstances have an impact on the care they deliver to their patients. This finding contradicts that of Nilsson and Stomberg²⁷, who found that opportunities for growth, working conditions, and supervision help to improve nurses' performance; it is also known that employees have problems when their working hours are extended beyond normal and when social conditions are poor²⁸. This is also in line with Herzberg²⁵, who stated that working circumstances are regarded as hygienic or unsatisfactory, and that if not met or present, individuals would not be motivated to achieve higher and better performance.

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Conclusion:

Financial incentives, a solid compensation structure, a suitable rating system, and acknowledgement of the nursing profession were found to be major drivers of motivation in our study. Knowledge of motivation and the elements that influence it will aid in the fight against Pakistan's human resource shortage.

Recommendations:

It is critical to know the reasons that affect nurse's job motivation and to develop a motivating plan to promote good aspects while overcoming negative ones. Workplace motivation and related aspects should be taught in nursing schools. Work motivation among nurses is a critical tool in managing nurse shortages, retention, migration, and leave in Pakistan.

Conflict of Interest

This study has no conflict of interest to be declared by any author.

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